
**Scientific
Report**

2016

LIBR

Laureate Institute for Brain Research
Improving Mental Health Through Neuroscience

IMPROVING
MENTAL
HEALTH THROUGH
NEUROSCIENCE

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LIBR

The Laureate Institute for Brain Research (LIBR) facilities consist of 28,000 square feet of space in a building that is attached to the Laureate Psychiatric Clinic and Hospital. The neuroimaging and laboratory facilities at LIBR are entirely dedicated to research. They include two MRI scanner bays and a control room, two video-teleconferencing-enabled group meeting sites, several medical examination and patient prep rooms, the computing facility, and ample office space for the investigators.

Details of LIBR facilities:

- 42 offices, including 1 large shared office for students and volunteers
- 4 conference rooms
- 2 MRI bays and adjoining control rooms
- 3 psychophysiological testing rooms
- 1 behavioral observation room
- 2 medical/blood draw rooms
- 1 mock scanner room
- 1 neuropsychological testing room
- 1 transcranial magnetic stimulation (TMS) room

We are fortunate to look back on another highly productive year at LIBR. The Institute continues to gain prominence and distinguish itself in the field of psychiatric research through a variety of efforts. Our investigators published over 50 research articles in top-tier, peer-reviewed journals, and LIBR's work has been featured in a number of local, national and international publications.

Martin Paulus, M.D.
Scientific Director and President
LIBR

The primary highlight, over the past year, is the tremendous progress made implementing the Adolescent Brain and Cognitive Development (ABCD) study, the largest neuroimaging study of adolescent brain development undertaken by the National Institutes of Health. LIBR has been among the most successful sites in recruiting youngsters (9-10 year olds) and their parents, thanks to the efforts of our outstanding study coordinator, Florence Breslin. The ABCD study will provide an unprecedented opportunity to examine how mood and anxiety disorders emerge during adolescence, how they affect the brain and how they resolve with treatment. Because of the ABCD study, we will be able to make unique and important discoveries in mental health that would have been unthinkable in any other research setting. In addition, LIBR, part of the 23-site ABCD consortium which includes, among others, University of California- Los Angeles, Washington University, University of Michigan, Yale University and Mount Sinai, plays an increasingly critical role and is recognized as a leading site for neuroimaging research.

Second, the Tulsa 1000 (T-1000) study, which aims to identify objective biological markers for mood, anxiety, substance use and eating disorders is well underway. In fact, we are projecting to be at the halfway mark of 500 research participants by early 2017. Our preliminary analyses have already resulted in several manuscripts and publications focused on identifying how individuals with depression and anxiety process information differently. The first goal

will be to determine whether we can identify different biotypes of depression. One way to think about this is to use the analogy of cough and fever in medicine. We know that different types of diseases can generate similar symptoms, but that providing the optimal treatment depends on knowing the precise underlying cause. Although more research is needed to identify the precise pathways underlying depression, we hope to use our data to differentiate individuals who present with depression based on their patterns of brain activity and their behavioral characteristics. The ultimate goal for this first step is to robustly identify different subtypes, which could otherwise not be detected. The next step will be to determine whether these subtypes show a different course of illness and respond to different types of interventions.

In the era of "big data," which we have entered with the T-1000 study, a strong data analytics team is critical. We have assembled talent to form our team led by computer scientist Rayus Kuplicki, Ph.D. Moreover, we were fortunate to add a first-rank statistician, Henry Yeh, Ph.D., who joined us from the University of Kansas Medical Center. He has implemented state-of-the-art statistical analysis procedures, critically important to establish subtypes of depression. He provides support for our principal investigators by improving statistical designs and developing cutting edge statistical analyses. The data analytics team will develop state-of-the-art analysis pathways, which we will apply to mental health data on a large scale in the future.

LETTER FROM THE PRESIDENT

Our principal investigators continue to make progress in their programs of research:

Robin Aupperle, Ph.D.: Individualized Prevention and Treatment for Mood and Anxiety Disorders.

Mental health treatment is not suited to a one-size-fits-all approach and could benefit from personalization of treatment strategy and greater use of prevention efforts. Therefore, the Aupperle lab uses established behavioral interventions to identify the symptomatic, behavioral or brain-based characteristics that best predict who will respond to what type of intervention. Similarly, Dr. Aupperle examines whether established behavioral interventions can be used to prevent the emergence of mental health problems in high-risk populations. This research will provide the empirical basis for individualized prevention and treatment of mental health problems in general, and mood or anxiety disorders in particular.

Jerzy Bodurka, Ph.D.: Applications of Real-time Brain Imaging to Mental Health.

The understanding of the living brain as it relates to mental health or disease is at its infancy. The Bodurka lab is developing new brain imaging tools to study the healthy and diseased brain. In particular, Dr. Bodurka is using real-time feedback from brain signals to train individuals or two interacting individuals on how to improve emotional regulation or social interaction. Ultimately, mental health researchers will utilize these methods to develop new treatments for patients with mood and anxiety disorders.

Yoon-Hee Cha, M.D.: Cerebellar Dysfunction and Neuromodulation in Anxiety and Depression.

Dr. Cha has been conducting research at LIBR for over four years and has been selected to become a LIBR principal investigator based on her important contributions to research, particularly in the area of TMS (transcranial magnetic stimulation). The cerebellum, an essential component of the brain's internal modeling machinery, helps individuals navigate their environments by continually comparing predicted versus actual experience. A dysfunction in modeling of either internal or external stimuli can lead to over-attention to behaviorally irrelevant information and have negative consequences on learning and extinction. The Cha lab uses transcranial magnetic and electrical current-based modulation of the cerebellum to examine the effects on these processes as they relate to mood and anxiety disorders, specifically on body motion perception and fear conditioning. This research will establish the biological basis for modulating the cerebellum as a novel treatment for functional brain disorders.

Justin Feinstein, Ph.D.: Floatation to Re-regulate the Brain-Body Relationship for Mental Health.

The brain is constantly flooded with outside stimulation interfering with direct communication between the brain and body, which is important for mental health. The Feinstein lab is using floatation exposure as a tool, which minimizes outside stimulation, to examine its effects on the brain using different methods (symptomatic assessments, behavioral tests, brain imaging and blood markers). This research will

establish the biological basis for how reduction of outside stimulation can be used to develop treatments for different mental health conditions, e.g. mood, anxiety and eating disorders.

Sahib Khalsa, M.D., Ph.D.: Brain-Heart Dysregulation and Mental Health.

The beating heart is sending one of the most important signals to the brain. The regulation between these organs is central for health and disease. The Khalsa lab uses an experimental medicine framework and pharmacological modulation of the heartbeat to examine the regulatory brain circuits using brain imaging. Dr. Khalsa hypothesizes that a dysregulated heart-brain relationship contributes to the onset and maintenance of several adverse mental health conditions, including mood, anxiety and eating disorders. By identifying how the brain and heart are dysregulated, this research will provide the biological basis for new treatments aimed at re-establishing a balanced regulation between these organs.

As the Institute matures, we strive toward implementing our discoveries to directly benefit patients, families and care providers. To that end, we are establishing a "Sandbox" clinic, which aims to provide patients with experimental diagnostic, prognostic or treatment tools, that have been developed at LIBR. Dr. Khalsa is taking the lead to establish the clinic at the Laureate Psychiatric Clinic and Hospital. Understanding the challenges that come with using scientific insights to improve mental health will help us to overcome the implementation barriers that prevent patients with mental illness from getting the best possible treatment they deserve.

Jonathan Savitz, Ph.D.: Inflammation and the Relationship to Depression.

Depression is the most devastating mental health problem on the planet, yet we know very little about the underlying disease process. The Savitz lab is examining whether inflammation of the brain is an underlying cause of depression. In particular, Dr. Savitz is using blood-based inflammatory and immune markers and experimental medicine designs to examine how inflammatory processes affect the brain in both healthy and depressed individuals. Ultimately, this research can help to identify new treatments for depression that are based on modifying the inflammatory process.

Kyle Simmons, Ph.D.: Brain-Body Dysregulation and Mental Health.

There is emerging evidence that a well-functioning relationship between the body and the brain is essential for mental health. The Simmons lab uses different methods (symptomatic assessments, behavioral tests, brain imaging and blood markers) to examine how signals from the body are processed in the brain, and how the dysfunction of these processes contributes to mood, anxiety and eating disorders. Ultimately, this research will help to establish the biological basis for developing new treatments that aim to re-establish a healthy relationship between the body and brain.

ABOUT LIBR

LIBR MISSION

A clinical neuroscience research institute that recognizes the dignity of each person, and leverages leading talent and technology to discover the causes of and cures for disorders of mood, anxiety, eating and memory.

SPECIFIC AIMS

Bring to bear a multidisciplinary research program aimed at illuminating the pathophysiology of neuropsychiatric disorders

Develop novel therapeutics, cures and preventions to improve the well-being of persons who suffer from or are at risk for neuropsychiatric disorders

Foster collaboration among scientists, clinicians and institutions engaged in research that enhances wellness and alleviates suffering from mental illness

HISTORY

LIBR opened on May 1, 2009, and currently houses a multidisciplinary team of scientists and clinical research staff who apply neuroimaging, genetic, pharmacological and neuropsychological tools to investigate the biology of neuropsychiatric disorders. The Institute's creation was supported by The William K. Warren Foundation for the purpose of conducting studies aimed at developing more effective treatments or prevention strategies for these disorders. The studies are led by scientists from diverse backgrounds, including physics, cognitive neuroscience, psychology, psychiatry, developmental neuroscience, computer science and genetics.

LIBR BY THE NUMBERS 2016

60 journal article publications by LIBR investigators

5,449 inquiries for study participation

2,480 participants enrolled across all studies

15 active grants and clinical trials

612 participants enrolled in their first MRI study

6 new externally funded grants

\$3.8 million in external grant funding

6 post-doctoral fellows

5 distinguished speakers for The William K. Warren Foundation 2016 lecture series

7 principal investigators

100+ poster presentations and talks at conferences and universities

6 staff scientists

1 associate adjunct investigator

52 collaborative institutions

6 graduate students

1,290 Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) scanning sessions

AREAS OF RESEARCH

The goal for LIBR is to generate impactful research (knowledge) that makes a difference in mental health. That is, the principal product of LIBR is knowledge building. In order for knowledge to be impactful, it needs to change behavior of the stakeholders and, as a consequence, improve the quality of life of the mentally ill. This change in behavior could be applying a new treatment, providing information to the patient that affects their behavior to improve outcomes, changing the strategy of treatment based on novel assessments or providing information about likely outcomes in the future. A critical task in creating impactful knowledge at LIBR is to shorten the gap of time between the acquisition of knowledge and the implementation in clinical practice. This gap of time will be greater if production of knowledge focuses on basic processes underlying the pathophysiology of the disorder as opposed to changing behavior. Therefore, we need to be mindful of creating knowledge that will affect mental health in the short-term as well as the long-term.

THERE IS A NEED FOR:

- 1** Earlier detection of the development and/or exacerbation of mental health conditions, e.g., early but not late stages of mood disorder may be treatable with an anti-inflammatory agent
- 2** Sensitive and specific tests for severity of mental health conditions, e.g., predicting relapse may allow the clinician to intervene earlier
- 3** Earlier and sensitive detectors of treatment effects of interventions for mental health conditions, e.g., rather than waiting four to six weeks for an antidepressant to show significant effects, early changes may help select treatments that work faster
- 4** Detection of the emergence of side effects
- 5** More effective interventions for anxiety, depression and substance disorders

BEHAVIORAL PROCESSES

This research theme focuses on identifying the physiological bases for drives and behaviors that contribute to the development, maintenance or recovery from neuropsychiatric dysfunction to improve the assessment and treatment of mental and physical health.

NEUROIMAGING

This research theme focuses on the existing and emerging tools and techniques in multimodal imaging.

NEUROMODULATION

This research theme focuses on real-time feedback modalities and non-invasive brain stimulation to change dysfunctional processes in psychiatric populations.

PSYCHOPHYSIOLOGY

This research theme focuses on the use of physiological measures to examine the connection between body and brain.

BIOASSAYS

This research theme focuses on the use of biochemical measures, ranging from inflammatory markers to microbiome assessments to genetics.

LIBR Administrative Staff

LIBR LEADERSHIP

Martin Paulus, M.D.
Scientific Director and President

Tom Cooper, MBA
Chief Executive Officer

Colleen McCallum, MBA
Chief Operating Officer

Jerzy Bodurka, Ph.D.
Chief Technology Officer

ABCD STUDY

The Adolescent Brain Cognitive Development (ABCD) study officially began enrollment at 16 of the 19 sites between September and December 2016, and added two additional sites for 2017. LIBR led the recruitment effort with 83 subjects during the first four months and was the only site to hit the NIH-directed goal of 85 percent recruitment during the ramp-up phase of enrollment.

Collaboration with the local school districts is critical to the success of the ABCD study. LIBR is proud of the support received. LIBR has students that represent 12 Tulsa public schools, four Sand Springs schools, two Jenks schools and every school in Broken Arrow. LIBR is also very grateful for the support of the local Native American community. LIBR has received additional IRB approval from the Cherokee Nation IRB, and 12 percent of the enrolled subject pool was recruited from the Indian Health Care Resource Center's youth wellness camps.

Adolescent Brain Cognitive Development
Teen Brains. Today's Science. Brighter Future.

T-1000 STUDY

Tulsa 1000 Study

The Tulsa 1000 (T-1000) study, the largest at LIBR, began in January 2015 and will continue enrolling participants through the end of 2018. Participants with mood, anxiety, eating and substance use disorders complete over 24 hours of baseline testing. This testing includes clinical interviews, behavioral and neuroimaging assessments of emotion, cognition, reward and interoception, one-hour follow-up interviews at three, six and nine months, and an eight-hour follow-up session at the one-year completion mark. The goal for this study is to determine whether neuroscience-based measures can be used to predict outcomes in patients with mental illness. In particular, we are trying to determine what factors best predict who will respond well to a particular treatment. **The study is a definitive step towards developing a science-based personalized medicine approach in mental health.**

In 2015, LIBR enrolled 164 of the 1,000 participants. In 2016, recruitment efforts substantially increased with 283 additional participants. Of the nearly 450 participants recruited over the first two years, LIBR's retention rate for the one-year follow-up session remains high at 94 percent retention. By diagnostic category, LIBR has enrolled 240 participants with mood and anxiety disorders, 133 with substance-use disorders, 26 with eating disorders and 48 healthy controls for comparison. LIBR's most successful recruitment strategies for mood and anxiety disorders and healthy control participants have been through radio and social media advertisements, and word-of-mouth. For substance use participants, LIBR works with invaluable community partners at the 12 & 12 treatment facility and Women in Recovery program through Family and Children's Services located in Tulsa, Okla. For eating disorder participants, LIBR has worked directly with the Laureate Psychiatric Clinic and Hospital and their outpatient treatment services. The T-1000 study is projected to reach the halfway point of enrolling 500 of the 1,000 participants by early 2017.

Awards

K23 awarded to Dr. Robin Aupperle

Congratulations to Dr. Robin Aupperle for receiving a Mentored Patient-Oriented Research Career Development Award (K23) from the National Institute of Mental Health. This award will support her research at LIBR studying brain-behavior relationships to develop highly targeted behavioral interventions for anxiety disorders that optimize treatment response.

Dr. Martin Paulus appointed to JAMA Psychiatry Editorial Board

Dr. Martin Paulus has been appointed to the Editorial Board at JAMA Psychiatry. This journal is the highest impact journal in psychiatry today. Dr. Paulus has reviewed articles on their behalf and because of the high quality, succinct and analytical reviews he provides, they invited him to formalize the relationship and secure his expertise.

This benefits LIBR in terms of increased visibility in the scientific community and new insight into cutting edge research underway globally.

Dr. Kyle Simmons receives research paper award

Dr. Kyle Simmons was awarded The University of Tulsa, Oxley College of Health Sciences, 2016 Research Award for the paper: "Depression-related Increases and Decreases in Appetite Reveal Dissociable Patterns of Aberrant Activity in Reward and Interoceptive Neurocircuitry," published in The American Journal of Psychiatry.

Dr. Jonathan Savitz awarded tenure at The University of Tulsa

Congratulations to Dr. Jonathan Savitz for successfully obtaining tenure at The University of Tulsa, Oxley College of Health Sciences.

Dr. Yoon-Hee Cha receives NARSAD award

Congratulations to Dr. Yoon-Hee Cha for being selected as a 2016 NARSAD Young Investigator grantee by the Brain and Behavior Research Foundation. Dr. Cha will investigate the potential for transcranial magnetic stimulation (TMS), a noninvasive technique, to treat chronic fear by altering brain activity. Her research aims to identify a therapeutic pathway to difficult-to-reach brain networks that can be targeted to treat anxiety.

INTEROCEPTION SUMMIT

Interoception is how the brain uses information from the body to process emotions and adapt to the environment. Interoception is becoming an increasingly important construct for a number of different mental health conditions, such as anxiety, mood, eating and addictive disorders due in part to findings highlighting its integral role in emotional experience, consciousness, self-regulation and decision-making. However, a number of challenges have made it difficult for interoceptive constructs to be broadly applied in mental health. To this end, LIBR, with the generous support of The William K. Warren Foundation, organized the first Interoception Summit. This conference aimed to unite a multidisciplinary group of leading scientists and thought leaders, with the goal of accelerating progress in interoception research and ultimately improving mental health outcomes.

Location

The meeting occurred over a three-day period at the PostOak Lodge and Retreat, an event center overlooking downtown Tulsa. The conference activities included keynote presentations and roundtable workshop discussions. Audience participation was highly encouraged. There were ample opportunities for unstructured interactions and scientific discussion.

Keynote Speakers

Ralph Adolphs, Ph.D.
Oliver Cameron, M.D., Ph.D.
Hugo Critchley, M.D., Ph.D.

Purpose

The Interoception Summit addressed the following topics:

ASSESSMENT

How do scientific researchers integrate assessments of interoceptive dysfunction in target populations to study disease severity, treatment response and prognosis?

Speakers: Paul Davenport, Olga Pollatos, Jamie Rhudy, Wolf Mehling, Sahib Khalsa

INTEGRATION

What are the model systems that are ideal for studying interoception, such as animal and human disease models?

Speakers: Lawrence Schramm, Stephen Oppenheimer, Kalyanam Shivkumar, Richard Lane, Kyle Simmons

PSYCHOPATHOLOGY

How is interoceptive dysregulation linked to disorders of mental health, and how can interoceptive principles be applied during treatment?

Speakers: Andreas von Leupoldt, Ilse Van Diest, Jamie Feusner, Alicia Meuret, Justin Feinstein

ROADMAP

What are possible benchmarks for success? What pragmatic go or no-go decisions need to be made in interoception research as they apply to mental health?

Speakers: Martin Paulus, Omer Van den Bergh, Murray Stein, Michelle Craske, Charles Nemeroff

Planned Outcomes

CONFERENCE PROCEEDINGS

- workshop output from each individual group during the workshop presentations;
- conference video from keynote speakers, workshop presenters and workshop discussion; and
- all documents and professionally edited video will be made available to the public via the LIBR website and YouTube channel.

PUBLICATIONS

- conference proceedings will be formalized into one consensus statement (i.e., a white paper);
- the paper will represent the issues discussed at the meeting and will serve as an authoritative reference for other scientists and funding agencies; and
- all meeting and conference invitees will be invited to participate as co-authors.

A travel scholarship program brought graduate and post-doctoral trainees from all over the world to Tulsa and LIBR. Each awardee was provided a mentor during the conference, drawn from the distinguished speakers.

FLOAT CLINIC AND RESEARCH CENTER (FCRC)

LIBR is home to the world's first research laboratory investigating the effects of floatation therapy on both the body and brain, as well as exploring its potential as a therapeutic treatment for promoting mental health and healing in patients who suffer from anxiety and other forms of mental illness.

Floatation therapy allows the nervous system to naturally enter a relaxed physiological state by reducing stimulation from the external environment. All visual, auditory, thermal, tactile and proprioceptive input is minimized in our specially designed circular pools. Moreover, each pool is saturated with 2,000 pounds of Epsom salt, allowing individuals to effortlessly float in a solution of water that is denser than the Dead Sea.

Throughout the float, you are in full control of the experience. You can enter and exit the pool whenever you choose. You can also turn the lights on or off simply by waving your arms. The temperature of the water and the air is calibrated to match the temperature of your skin (about 95 degrees), allowing you to float without ever having to feel too warm or cold.

The FCRC is directed by Dr. Justin Feinstein and is now in its second year of operation. Based on initial studies, the float environment appears to rapidly reduce levels of

stress, allowing one's brain and body to enter a deep state of relaxation. In order to document these changes, LIBR has developed wireless and waterproof sensors to measure neural and physiological signals during the float itself, including blood pressure, heart rate, respiration, movement and EEG brain waves. Last year the FCRC completed the first brain imaging study examining the effects of floatation. Healthy individuals underwent an fMRI scan before and immediately after floating, and the initial data looks very promising, with several papers currently being written for publication about the effects of floating on the brain.

Building from this base of knowledge, the FCRC has recently commenced its first set of clinical float studies examining the effects of floatation therapy in individuals who have been chronically suffering from high levels of anxiety and stress, including patients with PTSD, panic disorder, generalized anxiety disorder and anorexia nervosa. Preliminary data has shown that floating seems to help these patients significantly reduce their stress and anxiety, while improving both mood and well-being. This unique program of research is just beginning, so please stay tuned to learn more about how floatation therapy works and how it can help those who suffer from anxiety and other forms of mental illness.

EEG-FMRI FACILITY

Established in July 2009 and in research operation since June 2010, the facility provides advanced, state-of-art MRI, functional MRI (fMRI) and electroencephalography (EEG) neuroimaging capabilities to non-invasively measure, quantify, modulate, and study normal and abnormal human brain structure and functions.

The facility provides all technology, tools and resources needed to conduct and support advanced brain neuroimaging studies focused on advancing clinical research to discover causes of, cures and novel interventions for disorders of mood, anxiety, eating and memory.

Both MRI scanners are fully dedicated to research. LIBR's main research approach to study human brain function is a combination of simultaneous EEG and fMRI, which provides a unique capacity to capture and measure brain activity at high spatial and temporal resolution.

Each MRI scanner is also equipped with a custom-made real-time scanning system, allowing for the management of large amounts of neuroimaging data, real-time fMRI (rtfMRI), real-time integration of physiological data (respiration, pulse oximetry or ECG waveforms) and EEG data simultaneously acquired with fMRI, and neurofeedback (rtfMRI-nf) experiments to modulate and influence brain activity during subject scanning. Both scanners are also synchronized and integrated to conduct multimodal simultaneous EEG and fMRI hyperscanning experiments where two or more subjects' EEG and/or fMRI responses and their interactions are measured simultaneously. This advanced combination and customization of state-of-the-art MRI, RF coils and EEG technologies, along with custom-developed software solutions and a wide range of auxiliary computerized equipment, offer unique potential for conducting advanced brain research.

In the state of Oklahoma, the LIBR EEG-fMRI facility is the only facility that provides this unique technology and know-how to conduct advanced non-invasive research for studying the human brain.

The MRI facility was created and is overseen by Jerzy Bodurka, Ph.D., an expert in MRI/EEG-fMRI/real-time fMRI. It is also staffed by three staff scientists: Vadim Zotev, Ph.D. (physics), an expert in MRI, simultaneous EEG and fMRI, and fMRI data analysis; Qingfei Luo, Ph.D. (physics) an expert in EEG and fMRI and quantitative MRI (arterial spin labeling); and Masaya Misaki, Ph.D. (computational neuroscience), an expert in structural MRI image, real-time fMRI processing as well as fMRI decoding and multivariate multimodal fMRI/EEG data analysis. Other staff include four MRI technologists (Julie Owen, Leslie Walker, Tressia Lewis, and Julie Crawford), and a computer programmer support (Raquel Phillips).

FUNDING SOURCES

ACTIVE AND AWARDED GRANTS

National Institutes of Health (NIH)

Adolescent Brain Cognitive Development (ABCD) study
10/01/2015 – 09/30/2020
PI: Martin Paulus, M.D.

National Institute for Mental Health (NIMH)

The neural bases of pathological food perception and choice in major depression
05/01/2012 – 04/30/2017
PI: Kyle Simmons, Ph.D.

Neuroimaging abnormalities in major depressive disorder: effect of inflammation
09/12/2012 – 07/31/2017
PI: Jonathan Savitz, Ph.D.

Inflammatory transcripts, genes and positive valence system function in anhedonia
09/01/2012 – 07/01/2017
PI: Jerzy Bodurka, Ph.D.

NIH/NIMH: Mentored Patient-Oriented Research Career Development (K23)

Approach-Avoidance Conflict – a multi-level predictor for exposure therapy response
02/01/2016 – 01/30/2018
PI: Robin Aupperle, Ph.D.

Department of Defense (DoD)

Emotion regulation training for treating warfighters with combat-related PTSD using real-time fMRI and EEG assisted neurofeedback
09/30/2012 – 09/30/2017
PI: Jerzy Bodurka, Ph.D.

Brain and Behavior Research Foundation (formerly NARSAD)

Examining the neural basis of interoceptive fear
01/01/2015 – 01/01/2017
PI: Justin Feinstein, Ph.D.

Interoceptive learning and recall in major depression
02/01/2015 – 01/30/2017
PI: Kyle Simmons, Ph.D.

Augmented interoceptive exposure training as a new treatment for anxiety in anorexia nervosa
01/01/2016 – 01/01/2018
PI: Sahib Khalsa, M.D., Ph.D.

Efficacy of influenza vaccine in major depressive disorder
02/01/2016 – 01/30/2018
PI: Jonathan Savitz, Ph.D.

Enhancing fear extinction through cerebellar neuromodulation
02/01/2016 – 01/30/2018
PI: Yoon-Hee Cha, M.D.

Springbank Foundation Expanding

Education and access to neuromodulation therapies for MDD
03/09/2016 – 03/08/2018
PI: Yoon-Hee Cha, M.D.

MdDS Balance Disorder Foundation

Development of biomarkers to refine neuromodulation treatment targets in MDD
08/01/2014 – 11/30/2016
PI: Yoon-Hee Cha, M.D.

National Science Foundation

Innovative, broadly accessible tools for brain imaging, decoding and modulation
08/01/2016 – 07/31/2019
PI: Yoon-Hee Cha, M.D.

Epsom Salt Council

Measuring magnesium absorption via a high concentration Epsom salt bath
06/15/2015 – 06/15/2017
PI: Justin Feinstein, Ph.D.

2016 DONORS

- John J. King, Jr.
- Saxifrage Summit Partnership, LTD
c/o John J. King, Jr.
- Christopher W. King
- CWK Ventures, LLC
c/o Christopher W. King
- Judith King
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- DWK Legacy, LTD
c/o Constance King Cowett
- Natalie Bryant
- W. Kelly Vandever Revocable Trust
- William K. Warren, Jr., LLC
- Stephen K. Warren, Trust A

CLINICAL COLLABORATORS

LIBR works closely with several clinical entities in Tulsa to recruit new participants to LIBR research studies.

Family and Children Services (FCS)

Family and Children's Services is devoted to helping families in crisis, and serving people struggling with mental illness, addiction and homelessness. They are committed to the families and individuals of the Tulsa area, helping over 110,000 individuals each year, or one in six Tulsans. As part of LIBR's collaboration, a LIBR assessment team member is stationed at FCS and regularly recruits individuals to participate in LIBR studies. Also this year, LIBR established a research partnership with the Family and Children's Services program Women in Recovery. The intensive outpatient program is an alternative for women facing long prison sentences for non-violent, drug-related offenses. This award-winning program is dedicated to changing the lives of women in Oklahoma and giving them the tools to become positive, contributing members of the community.

12 & 12

12 & 12 is an award-winning leader in the Tulsa community for addiction treatment and recovery services. Last year, they served over 1,600 clients in Oklahoma. This year, LIBR established a collaboration with Brad Collins, director of community relations/research and efficacy, who helps to recruit individuals with substance-related problems to participate in the T-1000 study.

Laureate Psychiatric Clinic and Hospital (LPCH)

LIBR has continued to work closely with our neighbors at the Laureate Psychiatric Clinic and Hospital. Through a "universal consent" process, we are able to reach out to Laureate patients to inquire about their interest in participating in research. We have extended our partnership to include monthly informational sessions on our research studies with participants in the Intensive Outpatient Programs to recruit individuals with substance use and mental health disorders in the Tulsa area.

2016 WKW SPEAKERS

February 2

Dr. Angela Vincent
*Antibodies to Neuronal Surface Proteins
in Neurological Diseases*

May 10

Dr. Alicia Meuret
Psychobiological Mechanisms of Fear Extinction

August 16

Dr. Daniel Tranel
The Brain's Moral Compass: Clues from Neuropsychology

October 11

Dr. Pierre Tariot
Preventing Alzheimer's: Pipedream or Possibility?

December 16

Dr. Rainer Goebel
*Methodological advances in real-time fMRI
for high-speed, high-resolution neurofeedback
and brain-computer interface applications*

2017 WKW Speakers

January 10 Dr. Rajita Sinha **August 8** Dr. Leanne Williams

March 7 Dr. Rita Goldstein **September 12** Dr. Elliot Stein

April 4 Dr. Robert Yolken **November 14** Dr. Alexander Bystritsky

May 9 Dr. John Krystal

2016 VISITING SCIENTISTS

LIBR welcomed several visiting scientists to the Institute in 2016.

Date	Speaker	Lecture Topic or Visit Purpose
April 26	Dr. Chris Glaze	<i>A bias-variance trade-off that governs individual differences in learning and decision-making</i>
May 26	Dr. Frederike Petzschner	<i>Predicting the World to Predicting the Body</i>
May 31	Dr. Flavio Frohlich	<i>Transcranial Current Stimulation: Cortical Oscillations as a Treatment Target</i>
June 20	Mr. Adam Chekroud	<i>Data-Driven Treatment Selection for Mental Illness</i>
August 9	Professor Wes Thompson	<i>Statistics in R & Machine Learning</i>
September 22	Mr. Bradford Martins	<i>Multi-Level Modeling of Resilience to Addiction Comorbidity Following Childhood Adversity</i>
October 5	Dr. Larry Frank	<i>Quantitative Neuroimaging with MRI</i>
November 14	Dr. Klaas Stephan	<i>Translational Neuromodeling Lecture</i>
December 2	Dr. Jon Howlett	<i>PTSD, Error-Driven Learning and Methylphenidate: An Application of Computational Psychopharmacology</i>

IN THE NEWS

Tulsa AFNI Bootcamp: April 18-22, 2016 | Scientific staff from LIBR attended an all-day, week-long AFNI Bootcamp at the University of Oklahoma–Tulsa campus from April 18-22 with Dr. Bob Cox and his colleagues from the Scientific and Statistical Computing Core (SSCC) of the National Institute of Mental Health Intramural Program. Participants learned how to process neuroimaging data using the AFNI (Analysis of Functional NeuroImages) software, including topics of alignment and registration of images, single and group subject analyses, regression analysis, region-of-interest analysis, SUMA processing, resting state processing, DTI, InstaCorr and connectivity analysis.

LIBR Investigators Present Talks at ADAA Conference

The Anxiety and Depression Association of America (ADAA) held its annual conference in April 2016 in Philadelphia. Dr. Martin Paulus presented career advice to trainees from across the country as part of the Early Career Special Interest Group luncheon. He also chaired a computational psychiatry symposium and presented a talk on early life stress and functional brain organization related to the development of drug-use-disorders. Drs. Sahib Khalsa and Robin Aupperle and several lab members also attended the conference and participated in symposiums and poster presentations.

Paper Published in Scientific Reports

Congratulations to Dr. Masaya Misaki and colleagues in Dr. Jerzy Bodurka's lab for their recent publication in *Scientific Reports*. This open access paper and is available to the public to read and share. Their novel analysis approach showed that in subjects with depression, symptoms of suicidal ideation and anhedonia (loss of feeling of pleasure) were associated with response variation in the right nucleus accumbens, an area of the brain that responds to rewarding stimuli.

TulsaKids Magazine: Understanding the Adolescent Brain

The March 2016 edition of *TulsaKids* magazine featured an interview with LIBR's Dr. Martin Paulus on "Understanding the Adolescent Brain," where he discussed the often competing halves of a child's brain, ways to engage and appeal to the developing brain, and why encouraging exercise and good nutrition are great starting points.

IN THE NEWS

HEALTHY BRAINS FOR A HEALTHY OKLAHOMA
Laureate Institute for Brain Research

January 26
Healthy Body, Healthy Brain
Kyle Simmons, PhD

February 23
How to Be an Emotion Coach for Kids and Teens
Amanda Morris, PhD

March 23
Substance Use and Your Child
Florence Breslin, MS, CCRP

April 27
ABCD Progress Update
Martin Paulus, MD

May 25
The Balanced Brain
Yoon-Hee Cha, MD

Location
LIBR Conference Room, 1st Floor
6655 South Yale
Tulsa, OK 74136

Time
6:00-8:00 pm

For More Info
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www.facebook.com/LIBResearch

TULSA'S LITTLE DRILLER
welcomes all parents, teachers, and learning enthusiasts to LIBR's 2017 lecture series on brain development in kids

Healthy Brains for a Healthy Oklahoma

LIBR and the Adolescent Brain Cognitive Development (ABCD) study group proudly presented the new lecture series in 2016: "Healthy Brains for a Healthy Oklahoma." This ongoing lecture series provides parents, teachers and community members with valuable information on brain development in children. The lectures are held every fourth Tuesday of the month in the second floor conference room at LIBR from 6:00-8:00 p.m.

TU (The University of Tulsa) Tough: Mental Toughness Training for College Success

Dr. Robin Aupperle began a study of stress and resiliency in college students at The University of Tulsa. The aims of this study are to assess the extent of psychological distress for incoming first-year students at The University of Tulsa; assess the impact of "mental toughness" training on the trajectory of psychological well-being and academic success; assess the impact of mental toughness training on neural and behavioral reactivity to affective stimuli and decisions; and to examine genetic markers of resiliency in college populations and interactions between genetic markers and response to mental toughness training.

New Book Chapter Published by Dr. Martin Paulus

Dr. Paulus and colleagues published a new book chapter titled *Call for Pragmatic Computational Psychiatry: Integrating Computational Approaches and Risk-Prediction Models and Disposing of Causality in Computational Psychiatry: New Perspectives on Mental Illness*. Below is an excerpt:

"Biological psychiatry is at an impasse. Despite several decades of intense research, few if any, biological parameters have contributed to a significant improvement in the life of a psychiatric patient. It is argued that this impasse may be a consequence of an obsessive focus on mechanisms. Alternatively, a risk-prediction framework provides a more pragmatic approach, because it aims to develop tests and measures, which generate clinically useful information. Computational approaches may have an important role to play here. This chapter presents an example of a risk-prediction framework, which shows that computational approaches provide a significant predictive advantage. Future directions and challenges are highlighted."

Computational Psychiatry: New Perspectives on Mental Illness

Over the next three years, 50 percent of the chapters will be available to the public on a monthly rotational basis.

FULL CITATION:

Paulus M.P.P., Huang C., Harle K.M. 2016. *Call for Pragmatic Computational Psychiatry: Integrating Computational Approaches and Risk-Prediction Models and Disposing of Causality in Computational Psychiatry: New Perspectives on Mental Illness*, edited by A.D. Redish and J.A. Gordon. *Strüngmann Forum Reports*, vol. 20, J. Lupp, series editor. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.

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Dr. Aupperle's research focuses on using neurocognitive methods to enhance understanding of anxiety, depression and trauma. She is particularly interested in:

- 1 The intersection between cognitive and emotional processing and how this may relate to the development and maintenance of anxiety, depression and trauma-related symptoms**
- 2 How knowledge from neuroscientific research may be used to enhance treatment and prevention efforts**

In regards to the former, she has conducted research related to neuropsychological correlates of trauma and posttraumatic stress disorder (PTSD), and has developed translational exploratory and decision-making tasks to better understand behavioral, physiological, and neural correlates of anxiety and depression. In regards to the latter, she has been involved in research investigating behavioral and neural mechanisms of current pharmacologic and behavioral treatments for anxiety, depression and trauma-related disorders. She is also actively involved in identifying factors that support resilience to college-related stress and strategies to optimize psychological well-being for students.

SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

Dr. Aupperle was born and raised in rural Oklahoma and obtained her bachelor's degree in psychology from Oklahoma State University. She received her master's and doctoral education in clinical health psychology at the University of Kansas, under the mentorship of Cary Savage, Ph.D., and Douglas Denney, Ph.D. Her graduate research and clinical education focused on neuropsychology, neuroimaging and anxiety disorders. She then continued out west to complete clinical internship at the VA San Diego Healthcare System, during which her training focused on clinical neuropsychology, cognitive rehabilitation and treatment of posttraumatic stress disorder (PTSD).

Dr. Aupperle remained in San Diego to complete a postdoctoral fellowship under the mentorship of Drs. Martin Paulus and Murray Stein, conducting research related to neural substrates of anxiety disorders and PTSD, with a particular emphasis on decision-making processes and treatment. She moved to Kansas City to join the University of Missouri-Kansas City (UMKC) department of psychology as assistant professor in August 2011. In August 2014, Dr. Aupperle joined LIBR in Tulsa, Okla., as assistant professor.

Dr. Aupperle has initiated research projects at LIBR investigating neurocognitive and behavioral predictors of treatment response to behavioral activation therapy for depression and exposure therapy for anxiety. In addition, she is taking the lead in LIBR projects investigating predictors of success for females enrolled in a criminal diversion program and factors related to mental health resiliency in college students.

SELECTED PUBLICATIONS

Aupperle R.L., Allard C.B., Grimes E.M., Simmons A.N., Flagan T., Cissell C.H., Thorp S.R., Norman S.B., Paulus M.P., Stein M.B. (2013). Neural responses during emotional processing before and after cognitive trauma therapy for battered women. *Psychiatry Research: Neuroimaging*, 214(1): 48-55. doi: 10.1016/j.pscychresns.2013.05.001

Aupperle R.L., Melrose A., Francisco A., Paulus M.P., Stein M.B. (2015). Neural substrates of approach-avoidance conflict decision-making. *Human Brain Mapping*, 36(2):449-62. doi:10.1002/hbm.22639 PMID: PMC4300249

Paulus M.P. and Aupperle R.L. (2015). Finding the balance between safety and threat may hold the key to success when treating PTSD. *American journal of psychiatry*, 172(12): 1173-1177. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1176/appi.ajp.2015.15101256>

Aupperle R.L., Stillman A.N., Simmons A.N., Paulus M.P., Stein M.S. (2016). Intimate Partner Violence PTSD and Neural Correlates of Inhibition. *Journal of Traumatic Stress*, 29 (1): 33-40. doi: 10.1002/jts.22068

Chryssikou L., Gorey C., Aupperle R.L. (2016). Anodal transcranial direct current stimulation over right dorsolateral prefrontal cortex alters decision making during approach-avoidance conflict. *Social Cognitive and Affective Neuroscience*: nsw140. doi: 10.1093/scan/nsw140.

Aupperle R.L., Morris A.S., Silk J.S., Criss M.M., Judah M., Eagleton S., Kirlic N., Byrd-Craven J., Philips R., Alvarez R.P. (2016). Neural Responses to Maternal Praise and Criticism: Relationship to Depression and Anxiety Symptoms in High-Risk Adolescent Girls. *NeuroImage: Clinical*, 11: 548-554. doi: 10.1016/j.nicl.2016.03.009

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Dr. Bodurka's research focuses on three main areas:

1 Non-invasive, multimodal neuroimaging method development and applications for studying brain function, including: structural and functional MRI (fMRI), real-time fMRI with neurofeedback, multimodal simultaneous electroencephalography (EEG) and fMRI brain imaging, real-time integration of fMRI and EEG data, simultaneous EEG and fMRI neurofeedback, and EEG and fMRI hyperscanning

2 Novel non-invasive brain neuromodulation and neuroenhancement approaches to better understand brain emotion regulation and social interactions in major depressive disorder (MDD) and post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD)

3 Translational approaches to discover and research novel therapeutic strategies to improve treatments by training and recovering healthy function of brain networks, and to improve psychotherapy by determining the neural features of socially interacting individuals in MDD and PTSD

SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

Dr. Bodurka has broad expertise in Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) and Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) physics. He received his doctorate degree in physics from the University of Nicolaus Copernicus in Torun, Poland and completed part of his postdoctoral training in NMR at the Department of Chemistry at Free University of Berlin, Germany. As a postdoctoral fellow at Medical College of Wisconsin, he received firm training in MRI technology and functional MRI (fMRI). As a staff scientist at the functional MRI Facility of the National Institute for Mental Health (NIMH), the National Institute of Neurological Disorders and Stroke (NINDS), and the National Institutes of Health (NIH), he was responsible for providing a state-of-the-art imaging environment for conducting advanced MRI and fMRI research. In 2007, for his development of a Scalable Multi-Channel MRI Data Acquisition System, he received NIH's Director Award for Advancements in MRI Parallel Imaging Technology. The advancements in MRI receiver and multi-element coils technologies allowed for major improvements in MRI signal-to-noise ratio and pushed spatial and temporal limits for both functional and anatomical imaging. He has also developed an advanced real-time software set-up to allow for conducting real-time fMRI with neurofeedback.

In 2009, Dr. Bodurka joined the newly established LIBR to create a state-of-the-art MRI/fMRI/EEG neuroimaging facility, and to establish multimodal brain neuroimaging program with the overall purpose of advancing clinical research focused on mental disorders, with a broad research goal of advancing our understanding and characterization of brain abnormalities due to mental illness.

SELECTED PUBLICATIONS

Zotev V, Yuan H, Misaki M, Phillips R, Young KD, Feldner MT, Bodurka J. Correlation between amygdala BOLD activity and frontal EEG asymmetry during real-time fMRI neurofeedback training in patients with depression. *Neuroimage Clin.* 2016 11:224-38. doi: 10.1016/j.nicl.2016.02.003.

Misaki M, Suzuki H, Savitz J, Drevets WC, Bodurka J. Individual Variations in Nucleus Accumbens Responses Associated with Major Depressive Disorder Symptoms. *Sci Rep.* 2016 Feb 16;6:21227. doi: 10.1038/srep21227.

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Real-time fMRI neurofeedback training of amygdala activity in patients with major depressive disorders. *PLOS One*, 9(2):e88785. Young K.D., Zotev V., Phillips R., Misaki M., Drevets W.C., Bodurka J. (2014).

Self-regulation of human brain activity using simultaneous real-time fMRI and EEG neurofeedback. *Neuroimage*, 85:985-995. Zotev V., Phillips R., Yuan H., Misaki M., Bodurka J. (2014).

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Dr. Cha's main research interests include:

- 1** Exploring the role of the cerebellum in regulating cerebral networks, especially as it pertains to anxiety and depression
- 2** Understanding the connection between motion perception disorders, anxiety and migraine headache
- 3** Using functional neuroimaging and EEG to guide neuromodulation treatment
- 4** Developing neuromodulation tools that can be accessible to more patients

SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

Dr. Yoon-Hee Cha is a neurologist with subspecialty training in neurotology. She completed her premedical studies at Stanford University graduating with a degree in biology with honors in 1995. She earned her medical degree from Mayo Medical School in 2001, which included a year of research at the National Institutes of Health (NIH) through the Howard-Hughes-NIH Research Scholars Program from 1998-1999. In 2002, she completed a preliminary year in internal medicine at the Brigham and Women's Hospital in Boston, Mass., before going on to complete her neurology residency training at the University of California-San Francisco in 2005, during which time she was chief resident from 2004-2005. From 2005-2007, she was the neurotology fellow at the University of California-Los Angeles where she trained with Dr. Robert W. Baloh with whom she worked on the genetics of episodic ataxia and vestibular migraine. At University of California-Los Angeles, she developed her interest in understanding the neurological basis of motion perception, which led to her current work using functional MRI, EEG and neuromodulation techniques, such as transcranial magnetic stimulation and transcranial electrical stimulation, to probe the biological basis of and treat disorders of motion perception. She joined LIBR in August 2012. Her current work focuses on a group of patients with a disorder of motion entrainment called mal de débarquement syndrome (MdDS) as well as disorders of spatial processing related to anxiety and migraine. Her work has expanded to include studies that explore the role of the cerebellum in mood and anxiety disorders, which has launched investigations into cerebellar structure and connectivity, and targeting the cerebellum in neuromodulation studies to modulate cerebral function.

LAB MEMBERS

Diamond Urbano
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SELECTED PUBLICATIONS

Randomized single blind sham controlled trial of adjunctive home-based tDCS after rTMS for Mal de Debarquement Syndrome: safety, efficacy, and participant satisfaction assessment. *Brain Stimulation* 9(4):537-44. Cha Y.H., Urbano D., Pariseau N. (2016).

Double-blind sham-controlled cross-over trial of repetitive transcranial magnetic stimulation for Mal de Debarquement Syndrome. *Otol Neurotology*. 37(6):805-12. Cha Y.H., Deblieck C., Wu A. (2016).

The relationship between symptom severity, stigma, illness intrusiveness and depression in Mal de Debarquement Syndrome. *J Health Psychol*. 21(7):1339-50. Arroll M.A., Attree E.A., Cha Y.H., Dancy C.P. (2016).

Mal de Debarquement Syndrome: New insights. *Ann N Y Acad Sci*. 1343:63-68. Cha Y.H. (2015).

Voxel based morphometry alterations in mal de debarquement syndrome. *PLoSOne*. 10(8):e0135021. Cha Y.H., Chakrapani S (2015).

Episodic ataxia type 1: clinical characterization, quality of life and genotype-phenotype correlation. *Brain*. 137(Pt 4):1009-18. Graves T.D., Cha Y.H., Hahn A.F., Barohn R., Salajegheh M.K., Griggs R.C., Bundy B.N., Jen J.C., Baloh R.W., Hanna M.G., CINCH Investigators (2014).

Lasting modulation effects of rTMS on neural activity and connectivity as revealed by resting-state EEG. *IEEE Trans Biomed Eng*. 61(7):2070-80. Ding L., Shou G., Yuan H., Urbano D., Cha Y.H. (2014).

RESEARCH COLLABORATORS

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Three main areas of research:

- 1** Develop floatation as a tool for reducing stress and enhancing well-being in individuals who suffer from anxiety
- 2** Use functional neuroimaging and the lesion method to help determine the causal source of anxiety in the human brain
- 3** Study how the brain dynamically maps the internal world of our body and determine how these maps are dysregulated in conditions of anxiety, and whether floatation therapy can help regulate these disturbances, allowing patients to reshape their internal experience

SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

Dr. Justin Feinstein joined the faculty of LIBR in December of 2013, after completing his Ph.D. in clinical neuropsychology at the University of Iowa, and his postdoctoral fellowship at the California Institute of Technology. He earned his undergraduate degree in cognitive neuroscience at the University of California-San Diego. His clinical internship occurred at the San Diego VA hospital and focused on the treatment of veterans with PTSD using prolonged exposure therapy.

Dr. Feinstein’s research utilizes the lesion method and functional neuroimaging to explore how the human brain produces primal states of emotion, with an emphasis on the neuroscience of fear and treatments that alleviate anxiety. His laboratory is interested in understanding the intimate connection between the body and the brain, and developing new technologies to help bring this connection to the forefront of awareness. To this end, he is exploring several new approaches that can selectively enhance “interoceptive awareness” in order to help patients with anxiety establish a healthier balance between their body and brain.

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SELECTED PUBLICATIONS

The human amygdala and the induction and experience of fear. *Current Biology*, 21, 34-38. Feinstein J.S., Adolphs R., Damasio A., Tranel D. (2011).

Fear and panic in humans with bilateral amygdala damage. *Nature Neuroscience*, 16, 270-272. Feinstein J.S., Buzza C., Hurlmann R., Follmer R.L., Dahdaleh N.S., Coryell W.H., Welsh M.J., Tranel D., Wemmie J.A. (2013).

Panic Anxiety in Humans with Bilateral Amygdala Lesions: Pharmacological Induction via Cardiorespiratory Interoceptive Pathways. *Journal of Neuroscience*, 36(12): 3559-3566. Khalsa S.S., Feinstein J.S., Wi L., Feusner J.D., Adolphs R., Hurlmann R. (2016).

The pathways of interoceptive awareness. *Nature Neuroscience*, 12, 1494-1496. Khalsa S.S., Rudrauf D., Feinstein J.S., Tranel D. (2009).

Sustained experience of emotion after loss of memory in patients with amnesia. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 107, 7674-7679. Feinstein J.S., Duff M.C., Tranel D. (2010).

Feelings without memory in Alzheimer Disease. *Cognitive and Behavioral Neurology*, 27(3), 117-29. Guzman-Velez E., Feinstein J.S., Tranel D. (2014).

Preserved emotional awareness of pain in a patient with extensive bilateral damage to the insula, anterior cingulate, and amygdala. *Brain Structure and Function*, 221, 1499-1511. Feinstein J.S., Khalsa S.S., Salomons T.V., Prkachin K.M., Frey-Law, L.A., Lee J.E., Tranel D., Rudrauf D. (2016).

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Dr. Khalsa's research explores three main questions:

- 1** How do we feel our heartbeat?
- 2** Is there dysfunctional cross talk between the heart and brain in psychiatric and cardiovascular illnesses?
- 3** How can we develop new treatments that re-establish a functional dialogue between the heart and brain?

Not Pictured: Valerie Upshaw and Mahlega Hassanpour

SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

Dr. Khalsa received a bachelor's degree in psychology from SUNY Stony Brook in 2002. He graduated from the medical scientist training program at the University of Iowa, receiving M.D. and Ph.D. (neuroscience) degrees in 2009. He completed his residency training in psychiatry at UCLA in 2013, serving as the program chief resident and chief resident in the UCLA Anxiety Disorders Clinic. At that time, he joined the department as a faculty member in the division of adult psychiatry at UCLA, becoming an assistant professor in residence in 2014.

Dr. Khalsa's research examines how people feel their heartbeat, how the human brain maps cardiac sensation, and whether there is dysfunctional cross talk between the heart and brain in psychiatric and cardiovascular illnesses. To approach these questions, his studies have examined the effects of aging, focal brain injury, cardiac dysfunction and long-term meditation practice on awareness of the heartbeat. Ongoing projects examine the neural basis of cardiac sensation, the neural basis of dysfunctional heart-brain communication in anorexia nervosa and depression, and the impact of cardiac arrhythmias on mental health. These studies aim to ultimately answer the question "How can we develop new treatments that re-establish a functional dialogue between the heart and brain?"

Dr. Khalsa's clinical expertise focuses on the assessment and treatment of anxiety disorders. As a faculty member, Dr. Khalsa served as associate director of the UCLA Anxiety Disorders Clinic, supervising resident physicians in the treatment of anxiety disorders. As founding director of the Healthy Hearts Behavioral Medicine Program, an interdisciplinary endeavor started with the UCLA Cardiac Arrhythmia Center, he specializes in treating anxiety and mood disorders in individuals with cardiac arrhythmias. He also worked as an attending psychiatrist in the UCLA OCD Intensive Outpatient Program.

In February 2015, Dr. Khalsa joined LIBR in Tulsa, Okla., as the director of clinical studies, and as an assistant professor (tenure track) at The University of Tulsa.

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SELECTED PUBLICATIONS

SELECTED PUBLICATIONS (IN 2016):

*Khalsa S.S., *Feinstein J.S., Li W., Feusner J.D., Adolphs R., Hurlmann R. Panic anxiety in humans with bilateral amygdala lesions: pharmacological induction via cardiorespiratory interoceptive pathways. *Journal of Neuroscience*. 2016 36: 3559-66. *Indicates equal contribution

Shivkumar K., Ajjola O.A., Anand I., Armour J.A., Chen P.S., Esler M.D., DeFerrari G., Fishbein M.C., Goldberger J.J., Harper R.M., Joyner M.J., Khalsa S.S., Kumar R., Lane R.D., Mahajan A., Po S., Schwartz P.J., Somers V., Valderrabano M., Vaseghi M., Zipes D. Clinical Neurocardiology—defining the value of neuroscience based cardiovascular therapeutics. *Journal of Physiology*. 2016 594:3911-54.

Khalsa S.S., Kumar R., Patel V., Strober M., Feusner, J.D. Mammillary body volume abnormalities in anorexia nervosa. *International Journal of Eating Disorders*. 2016 49: 920-9.

Khalsa S.S., Lapidus R. Can interoception improve the pragmatic search for biomarkers in psychiatry? *Frontiers in Psychiatry*. 2016 7:121.

Hassanpour M.S., Yan L.R., Wang, D.J., Lapidus R.C., Arevian A.C., Simmons W.K., Feusner J.D., Khalsa S.S. How the heart speaks to the brain: neural activity during cardiorespiratory interoceptive stimulation. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B*. 2016. 371: 20160017.

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Dr. Paulus' research focuses on three main areas:

- 1** Using neuroimaging to develop predictive biomarkers for anxiety disorders and addictive disorders
- 2** Using computational psychiatry to better quantify the behavioral dysfunctions in individuals with mood, anxiety and addictive disorders
- 3** Develop a research pipeline that enable one to translate basic neuroscience discoveries into clinically useful tools

SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

Dr. Paulus studied medicine at the Johannes Gutenberg University in Mainz from 1979-1985. He received a postdoctoral fellowship from the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (German research foundation) in 1986 to study the effects of calcium antagonists on animal models of mania at the University of California-San Diego (UCSD). In 1993, Dr. Paulus left UCSD to resume his medical training, and completed his internship at the Long Island Jewish Medical Center/ Zucker Hillside Hospital in Long Island, New York. In 1994, he rejoined the department of psychiatry at UCSD as a psychiatric resident. Dr. Paulus completed his residency in psychiatry in 1997. At that time, he joined the department of psychiatry at UCSD as an assistant professor and became a staff psychiatrist at the Veterans Affairs San Diego Health Care System (VASDHS). In May 2014, Dr. Paulus joined the LIBR in Tulsa, Okla., as the scientific director and president.

Dr. Paulus has published over 250 scientific papers, been funded continuously by federal grants since 1997 and is currently the principal investigator on a NIMH R01 aimed at determining the biological basis for positive and negative valence domains in anxiety and depression. He has served on numerous research panels, study sections and advisory committees. Currently, Dr. Paulus is conducting a large-scale study in Tulsa, the T-1000, to determine whether biological measures can be developed to help a clinician predict patient outcomes. Dr. Paulus is also a member of the Adolescent Brain Cognitive Development (ABCD) study, which aims to determine how the brain changes during the course of adolescence and how these changes put adolescents at risk for substance use.

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SELECTED PUBLICATIONS (IN 2015)

McAllister T.W., Zafonte R., Jain S., et al. Randomized Placebo-Controlled Trial of Methylphenidate or Galantamine for Persistent Emotional and Cognitive Symptoms Associated with PTSD and/or Traumatic Brain Injury. *Neuropsychopharmacology*. Sep 11 2015.

Huang H., Movellan J., Paulus M.P., Harle K.M. The Influence of Depression on Cognitive Control: Disambiguating Approach and Avoidance Tendencies. *PLoS One*. 2015;10(11):e0143714.

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Harle K.M., Stewart J.L., Zhang S., Tapert S.F., Yu A.J., Paulus M.P. Bayesian neural adjustment of inhibitory control predicts emergence of problem stimulant use. *Brain*. Sep 3 2015.

Paulus M.P. Pragmatism instead of mechanism: A call for impactful biological psychiatry. *JAMA Psychiatry*. 2015.

Gowin J.L., Ball T.M., Wittmann M., Tapert S.F., Paulus M.P. Individualized relapse prediction: Personality measures and striatal and insular activity during reward-processing robustly predict relapse. *Drug Alcohol Depend*. Apr 30 2015.

RESEARCH COLLABORATORS

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Dr. Savitz's work focuses on three main areas:

- 1** Understanding the impact of inflammatory mediators—particularly kynurenine pathway metabolites—on brain structure and function
- 2** Developing an experimental model of inflammation in order to evaluate how depressed patients with inflammation differ clinically, immunologically and neurophysiologically from non-depressed patients with inflammation
- 3** The identification of microbial pathogens that may be an upstream cause of depression and psychosis

SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

Dr. Savitz received an undergraduate degree at the University of the Witwatersrand in Johannesburg in psychology and genetics, performed further graduate work in neuropsychology, including a clinical internship, and then completed a doctorate's degree on the genetics of bipolar disorder at the University of Cape Town. He subsequently completed a post-doctoral fellowship in the Section of Neuroimaging of Mood and Anxiety Disorders within the National Institute of Mental Health's (NIMH) Mood and Anxiety Disorders Program, and is currently an assistant professor at the LIBR (LIBR) and The University of Tulsa. He has trained with two of the most well-known experts in their respective fields: Wayne Drevets (mood disorders, neuroimaging) and Robert Dantzer (psychoneuroimmunology), and has conducted a number of innovative studies that have addressed important gaps in our knowledge regarding the relationship between genes, immunological function and neuroimaging abnormalities in mood disorders.

Dr. Savitz has published over 50 first or senior author scientific papers in journals such as *Molecular Psychiatry*, *Biological Psychiatry*, and *Neuropsychopharmacology*, and is currently the principal investigator on several grants, including a K01 grant from the NIMH and a NARSAD Young Investigator Award. He is an associate editor of the scientific journal, *Neuroscience Letters*, and serves as a reviewer for numerous European and American grant agencies, including the MESH study section of the NIH. Dr. Savitz's research aims to delineate the underlying immunological abnormalities associated with major depressive disorder and bipolar disorder, and linking these molecular changes to brain structure and function. In this regard, he is working with Drs. Paulus and Irwin, from the University of California-Los Angeles, to initiate an experimental study using endotoxin to safely induce transient inflammation in people suffering from depression. He also is collaborating with Bob Yolken at Johns Hopkins University to identify microbes involved in psychiatric illness, and Janssen Pharmaceuticals on a project that aims to characterize autoimmune phenomena in people with depression and psychosis.

LAB MEMBERS

Bart Ford
Graduate Student
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Harvey Morris
Research Scientist

SELECTED PUBLICATIONS

- Mechawar N. and Savitz J. (2016). Neuropathology of Mood Disorders: Do we see the stigmata of inflammation? *Translational Psychiatry*. 6, e946.
- Young K.D., Drevets W.C., Dantzer R., Teague T.K., Bodurka J., Savitz J. (2016). Kynurenine Pathway Metabolites are Associated with Hippocampal Activity during Autobiographical Memory Recall in Patients with Depression. *Brain Behavior and Immunity*. 56, 335-342.
- Meier T.B., Drevets W.C., Wurfel B.E., Ford B.N., Morris H.M., Victor T.A., Bodurka J., Teague T.K., Dantzer R., Savitz J. (2016). Relationship between neurotoxic kynurenine metabolites and reductions in right medial prefrontal cortical thickness in major depressive disorder. *Brain Behavior and Immunity*. 53, 39-48.
- Singh R., Savitz J., Teague T.K., Polanski D.W., Mayer A.R., Bellgowan P.S.F., Meier T.B. (2016). Mood symptoms correlate with kynurenine pathway metabolites following sports-related concussion. *Journal of Neurology, Neurosurgery, and Psychiatry*. 87, 670-675.
- Meier T.B., Savitz J., Singh R., Teague T.K., Bellgowan P.S.F. (2016). Smaller Dentate Gyrus and CA 2 & 3 volumes are associated with kynurenine metabolites in collegiate football athletes. *Journal of Neurotrauma*. 33, 1349-57.
- Victor T.A., Drevets W.C., Misaki M., Bodurka J., Savitz J. (2017) Sex Differences in Neural Responses to Subliminal Sad and Happy Faces in Healthy Individuals: Implications for Depression. *Journal of Neuroscience Research*. 95(1-2):703-710.
- Meier M.B., Lancaster M.A., Mayer A.R., Teague T.K., Savitz J. Abnormalities in functional connectivity in collegiate football athletes with and without a concussion history: implications and role of neuroactive kynurenine pathway metabolites. *Journal of Neurotrauma*. In press.
- Cho H.J., Savitz J., Dantzer R., Teague T.K., Drevets W.C., Irwin M.R. (2017) Sleep Disturbance and Kynurenine Metabolism in Depression. *Journal of Psychosomatic Research*. In press.

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Dr. Simmons' research focuses on three main areas:

- 1** Why is it that some individuals lose their appetite when they get depressed, and others eat more? Can these changes in eating behavior, or biological markers of how the body and brain use energy, serve as early indicators of depression onset, improvement or recurrence?
- 2** What role does brain-body communication play in the development, course and outcome of eating disorders? Can changes in body awareness tell us something about recovery from anorexia nervosa?
- 3** How does drug craving, such as in nicotine addiction, co-opt brain systems that sense the body's needs and organize behaviors to meet those needs?

SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

Dr. Simmons completed his master's degree in clinical psychology (2001) and his doctorate's (2005) in cognitive psychology at Emory University. He then completed his postdoctoral fellowship under the direction of Dr. Alex Martin in the Laboratory of Brain and Cognition, within the National Institute of Mental Health (NIMH) intramural research program (2005-2009). In 2009, Dr. Simmons was recruited to Tulsa where he now directs the Appetitive and Interoceptive Psychopathology Lab at LIBR.

Dr. Simmons' research falls generally within two domains. One is the neural basis of the conceptual representations underlying humans' food knowledge. In a second domain of research, Dr. Simmons' lab is examining the functional organization of the insular cortex, with particular attention to the insula's role in monitoring the physiological state of the body, otherwise known as interoception.

Both domains of research are highly related, as the insula plays an important role in food motivation and gustatory representation, and interoception is an important component in satiety signaling. The common goal of these two lines of research is to elucidate how the body's homeostatic state influences food reward representation and food-related decision-making, both normatively and in psychiatric illness.

SELECTED PUBLICATIONS

Kerr K.L., Avery J.A., Moseman S.E., Bodurka J., Zucker N.L., Simmons W.K., (2016) Altered insula activity during visceral interoception in weight-restored patients with anorexia nervosa. *Neuropsychopharmacology*, 41, 521-528.

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Kleckner I.R., Wormwood J.B., Simmons W.K., Feldman Bartett L., Quigley K.S., (in press). Methodological and Analytical Recommendations for a Heartbeat Detection-Based Measure of Interoceptive Sensitivity. *Psychophysiology*

Puhl M., Coberly W.A., Gotts S.J., Simmons W.K., (in press). L1 Regularized Regression Modeling of Functional Connectivity. In C. Constanda, A. Kirsch, (Eds.), *Integral Methods in Science and Engineering*. pp.515 - 526. Basel: Birkhauser Press.

Hassanpour M.S., Yan L.R., Wang D.J., Lapidus R.C., Arevian A.C., Simmons W.K., Feusner, J.D., Khalsa, S.S. (in press) How the heart speaks to the brain: neural activity during cardiorespiratory interoceptive stimulation. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B*.

Avery J.A., Burrows K., Kerr K.L., Bodurka J., Khalsa S., Paulus M.P., Simmons W.K. (in press). How the brain wants what the body needs: the neural basis of positive alliesthesia. *Neuropsychopharmacology*

Avery J.A., Gotts S.J., Kerr K.L., Burrows K., Ingeholm J.I., Bodurka J., Martin A., Simmons W.K. (in press). Convergent gustatory and viscerosensory processing in the human dorsal mid-insula. *Human Brain Mapping*

Kleckner I.R., Zhang J., Touroutoglou A., Chanes L., Xia C., Simmons W.K., Quigley K.S., Dickerson B.C., Barrett L.F. (in press). Evidence for a Large-Scale Brain System Supporting Allostasis and Interoception in Humans. *Nature Human Behavior*

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- Kara Kerr**
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- Katie Thompson**
Psychiatric Research
Coordinator

Ongoing Studies

If you are interested in participating in any of the studies below, or would like to be considered for future studies, please call our Assessment Team at 918-502-5100 or email info@laureateinstitute.org.

Call 918-240-2583 or Email cwohlab@libr.net

Laureate Institute for Brain Research - 6655 South Yale Ave - Tulsa, OK 74136
Visit us online at www.laureateinstitute.org

Are You Depressed?

Help us understand how the brain functions in individuals with Major Depressive Disorder (MDD)

ABOUT OUR RESEARCH

The Laureate Institute for Brain Research (LIBR) is studying the biological basis of Major Depressive Disorder (MDD).

We conduct research using magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) to make images of the brain.

These images help researchers understand how the brain processes emotion and motivation.

MRI is safe, painless, and involves no radiation.

WE NEED YOU

You are eligible if you are:

- male or female
- currently depressed
- ages 18-55
- not currently taking psychiatric medication

Joining this research study provides you with an opportunity to contribute to the understanding of MDD, which affects millions of Americans.

Compensation is provided.

SYMPTOMS OF MDD MAY INCLUDE:

Sadness
Hopelessness
Depressed mood
Problems sleeping
Difficulty concentrating
Lack of motivation

For more information, please call LIBR at: **918-502-5100**

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ABOUT OUR RESEARCH

The Laureate Institute for Brain Research (LIBR) aims to discover the biological basis for psychiatric disorders such as Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD).

We conduct research using magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) to make images of the brain.

These images help researchers understand how the brain processes emotion and stress.

MRI is safe, painless, and involves no radiation.

WE NEED YOU

You are eligible if you:

- are male
- a combat veteran
- ages 18-55
- have been diagnosed with PTSD
- are not currently taking psychiatric medication

Joining this research study provides you with an opportunity to contribute to the understanding of PTSD, which affects thousands of veterans.

Compensation is provided.

SYMPTOMS OF PTSD MAY INCLUDE:

Flashbacks
Anxiety
Depression
Insomnia
Nightmares
Irritability
Social Withdrawal

For more information, please call LIBR at: **918-502-5159**

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Visit us online at www.laureateinstitute.org or email PTSDvets@laureateinstitute.org

ABOUT OUR RESEARCH

This study aims to explore how effective Behavioral Activation Depression Therapy is in reducing symptoms of depression.

As a participant you will receive 10 weeks of therapy and complete tasks, questionnaires, blood draws, and EEG.

To see what's happening in your brain we will use magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), a very safe technology that takes live images of your brain as it's working.

Compensation will be provided.

ABOUT THE THERAPY

Depressive symptoms can impact our day-to-day behavior. Feeling down or depressed, and tired all of the time can reduce our desire to seek out and enjoy daily activities. The fewer things we enjoy, the more down or depressed we may feel.

Behavioral activation breaks this vicious cycle by providing opportunities and motivation to engage in more pleasurable and rewarding activities. Behavioral activation also helps us tackle those daunting to-do lists by breaking activities down in a manageable and realistic way.

WE NEED YOU

You may be eligible for this study if you are:

- 18 to 55 years old
- male OR female
- depressed

SYMPTOMS OF DEPRESSION

Loss of pleasure in things you used to enjoy, difficulty sleeping, feeling depressed or blue, changes in weight or appetite, difficulty concentrating, decreased energy or fatigue, moving or talking more slowly.

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VOLUNTEER for the TULSA 1000 STUDY

Let's bring mental health into the 21st century by helping us develop the world's first "EKG for the psychiatrist"

ABOUT OUR RESEARCH

LIBR is a scientific research institute that focuses on discovering brain-based technologies to improve mental health.

LIBR is unique in a number of different ways.

First, it challenges its scientists to think outside the box to come up with game changing research findings that improve mental health care.

Second, it closely works with the Laureate Psychiatric Clinic and Hospital next door to develop new treatments for psychiatric patients.

Third, it has one of the best brain imaging facilities in the country to study the living brain.

PARTICIPATION

The Tulsa 1000 (or T-1000) study involves five timepoints over the course of one year, including a series of baseline visits and 4 follow-up sessions involving:

- psychiatric assessments
- behavioral testing
- brain imaging scans and tasks
- blood marker testing

All study assessments and procedures will be provided free of charge to you.

You will be paid for your time spent participating in the Tulsa 1000 study.

WE NEED YOU

Qualified volunteers will:

- Be ages 18-55, male or female
- Have problems with: depression, anxiety, substance use or eating behavior

OR

Be free of psychiatric symptoms

Joining this research study helps us move toward our goal of personalizing mental health care.

For more information, please call LIBR at: **918-502-5100**

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JOIN THE FUN @ LIBR

Tulsa's Little Driller and the Laureate Institute for Brain Research are looking for 8-10 year olds for a study on brain development.

Compensation is provided for participation.

918-502-ABCD

E-mail abcd@libr.net | 6655 South Yale Ave, Tulsa, OK 74136

ABOUT OUR RESEARCH

This study aims to explore how anxiety relates to the way we think, feel, and make decisions, as well as how our brain responds to various situations.

As a participant you will complete tasks that trigger parts of your brain involved in decision making and other thought processes.

To see what's happening in your brain, we will use magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), a very safe technology that takes live images of your brain as it's working.

WE NEED YOU

You may be eligible for this study if you:

- Are 18 to 55 years old
- Are male OR female
- Experience high anxiety

OR

Do not experience any significant mental health symptoms.

You will be paid for your participation.

SYMPTOMS OF ANXIETY

Fear of or distress in social situations, such as public speaking

Fear of or distress in performance situations, such as taking tests

Exaggerated or persistent worry about a number of different aspects of life

Panic attacks
Muscle tension
Difficulty sleeping
Irritability

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2016 PUBLICATIONS

Aupperle R.L., Morris A.S., Silk J.S., Criss M.M., Judah M.R., Eagleton S.G., Kirlic N., Byrd-Craven J., Phillips R., Alvarez R.P. Neural responses to maternal praise and criticism: Relationship to depression and anxiety symptoms in high-risk adolescent girls. *Neuroimage Clin.* 2016 Apr 4;11:548-54.

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Avery J.A., Burrows K., Kerr K.L., Bodurka J., Khalsa S.S., Paulus M.P., Simmons W.K. How the brain wants what the body needs: The neural basis of positive alliesthesia. *Neuropsychopharmacology.* 2016;42(4):822-830.

Cha Y.H., Deblieck C., Wu A. Double-blind sham-controlled cross-over trial of repetitive transcranial magnetic stimulation for Mal de Debarquement Syndrome. *Otol Neurotol.* 2016 Jul;37(6):805-12.

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*Khalsa S.S., *Feinstein J.S., Li W., Feusner J.D., Adolphs R., Hurlmann R. Panic anxiety in humans with bilateral amygdala lesions: Pharmacological induction via cardiorespiratory interoceptive pathways. *J Neurosci.* 2016 Mar 23;36(12):3559-66. *Indicates equal contribution

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Mayeli A., Zotev V., Refai H., Bodurka J. Real-time EEG artifact correction during fMRI using ICA. *J Neurosci Methods.* 2016 Dec 1;274:27-37.

Mechawar N., Savitz J. Neuropathology of mood disorders: Do we see the stigmata of inflammation? *Transl Psychiatry.* 2016 Nov 8;6(11):e946.

Misaki M., Suzuki H., Savitz J., Drevets W.C., Bodurka J. Individual variations in nucleus accumbens responses associated with major depressive disorder symptoms. *Sci Rep.* 2016 Feb 16;6:21227.

Paulus M.P. Neural basis of mindfulness interventions that moderate the impact of stress on the brain. *Neuropsychopharmacology.* 2016 Jan;41(1):373.

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Simmons W.K., Burrows K., Avery J.A., Kerr K.L., Bodurka J., Savage C.R., Drevets W.C. Depression-related increases and decreases in appetite: Dissociable patterns of aberrant activity in reward and interoceptive neurocircuitry. *Am J Psychiatry.* 2016 Apr 1;173(4):418-28.

Victor T.A., Drevets W.C., Misaki M., Bodurka J., Savitz J. Sex differences in neural responses to subliminal sad and happy faces in healthy individuals: Implications for depression. *J Neurosci Res.* 2016;95(1-2):703-710.

Wong C.K., Zotev V., Misaki M., Phillips R., Luo Q., Bodurka J. Automatic EEG-assisted retrospective motion correction for fMRI (aE-REMCOR). *Neuroimage.* 2016 Apr 1;129:133-47.

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Zotev V., Yuan H., Misaki M., Phillips R., Young K.D., Feldner M.T., Bodurka J. Correlation between amygdala BOLD activity and frontal EEG asymmetry during real-time fMRI neurofeedback training in patients with depression. *Neuroimage Clin.* 2016 Feb 12;11:224-38.

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